

CAN CRP/ALBUMIN RATIO PREDICT IN-HOSPITAL AND 30-DAY MORTALITY IN ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE PATIENTS

Fatma Özpamuk Karadeniz¹, Emine Altuntaş²

¹Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Cardiology, Karaman, Turkey

²Sancaktepe Professor Dr. İlhan Varank Training and Research Hospital, Department of Cardiology, İstanbul, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Purpose: Inflammation plays a pivotal role development of both acute ischemic stroke(AIS) and atherosclerosis. It has been shown that the CRP (C-reactive protein (CRP)/albumin ratio (CAR), calculated by dividing CRP by albumin, is a good indicator of the level of inflammation. In this study, we planned to investigate whether CAR has an effect on in-hospital and 30-day major adverse cardiovascular events(MACE) in AIS patients.

Methods: We retrospectively enrolled 209 AIS patients. The patient group was classified into two groups according to CAR levels. These groups were compared in terms of C-reactive protein, albumin, CAR, and other hematologic inflammatory parameters. In-hospital and 30-day MACE was recorded.

Results: In-hospital and one-month follow-up, a total of 35 MACE was developed. In-hospital and 30- day MACE was significantly higher in high CAR patients with high CRP values and low albumin levels.

Conclusion: Our study demonstrated that a high CAR value is an independent predictor of in-hospital and 30-day mortality in patients with AIS.

Keywords: Acute ischemic stroke, CRP/albumin ratio, Major adverse cardiovascular event

INTRODUCTION

Acute ischemic stroke (AIS) is one of the major causes of death and disability worldwide [1]. Ischemic stroke accounts for approximately 90% of all strokes [2]. In the last decades, as a result of advances in diagnosis and interventional treatment, a decrease in AIS mortality and morbidity rates is observed. Chronic inflammation has a significant role in the pathophysiology of AIS [3]. Inflammatory biomarkers predict the development of atherothrombotic events and short and long-term mortality after acute stroke.

Increased C-reactive protein (CRP) levels have been shown to predict both the risk of future stroke and the risk of death after stroke [4]. Albumin decreases as a negative acute phase reactant in acute illnesses including AIS [5]. Albumin also shows the nutritional status of AIS patients and decreases as a result of malnutrition [6]. For these reasons, decreased albumin levels were shown with poor outcomes in AIS patients [7].

CRP/ albumin ratio (CAR) was calculated by dividing the serum CRP level to the serum albumin level. The level of CRP increases in proportion to the inflammation in the serum, and the level of albumin decreases, which causes an increase in CAR. Increased CAR was found an increased 90- day mortality risk in AIS patients [8]. The relationship between both CRP and albumin levels and in-hospital were shown separately in AIS patients. However, CRP to albumin ratio (CAR), a newly defined inflammation and nutrition-based risk score, has not yet been sufficiently studied. In this study, we planned to investigate the possible relationship between CAR level and in-hospital and post-hospital 30-day mortality in AIS patients.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study populations

Between September 2019 and January 2022, 209 consecutive patients with acute ischemic stroke (age 18–90 years) were retrospectively enrolled. Acute stroke was defined as the presence of occlusion in the vessels supplying blood flow to the brain, with imaging findings on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or computed tomography (CT) scans, and a new neurological defect that develops within 24 hours. The patient group in our study was divided into two groups according to the development of mortality or not. CAR score was calculated according to the admission C-reactive protein and serum albumin level. Exclusion criteria were: age under 18 years, changes in inflammatory or immune markers other than CVE (e.g., autoimmune diseases, sepsis, trauma, recent major surgery, active malignancy), glomerular filtration rate <30 ml/min, receiving thrombolytic therapy, and pregnancy. Our study was carried out in full compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethics committee approval was obtained for our study [Decision number 09-2022/5].

Demographic characteristics of patients such as age, gender, and individual risk factors were scanned from hospital records.

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Blood sample test analysis

Fasting blood samples were taken from arm veins. Cobas 6000 Roche was used to measure fasting glucose level, cholesterol panel, and renal function tests. The auto hematology analyser (BC6800 Mindray Medical Electronics Co. Shenzhen, China) was used to measure the complete blood count parameters. This formula was used to calculate SII index: $(SII = \text{platelet count} \times \text{neutrophil count} / \text{lymphocyte count})$. This formula was used to calculate the neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR): $\text{neutrophil counts} / \text{lymphocyte counts}$ (NLR).

Transthoracic echocardiography

Echocardiography was performed using the Vivid 5 device ((Vivid 5; GE Healthcare, Inc. Chicago, IL, USA) with a 2.5 MHz transducer. All axes including parasternal long and short axis, and apical views were used to assess cardiac structures. The modified Simpson method was used to assess ejection fraction (EF).

Follow-up and study endpoints

Clinical endpoints in the study included all-cause mortality and major adverse cardiovascular event (MACE). We assessed in-hospital mortality (during the hospital stay). All-cause mortality was the primary endpoint of the study. The major adverse cardiovascular event (MACE) composite of rehospitalisation for severe heart failure, nonfatal MI, and nonfatal stroke. New York Heart Association (NYHA) stage 4 heart failure patients were classified as advanced heart failure. European Society of Cardiology guidelines including the non-ST elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) guideline published in 2020 and the ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) guideline published in 2017 was used to diagnose of acute myocardial infarction [9, 10].

All-cause mortality was defined as death from any cause in-hospital follow-up. Hospital records and national patient records were reviewed to assess primary clinical outcomes and mortality.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows 18.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). CAR cut-off value was determined as 0.01752 according to the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) analysis. Accordingly, patients with >0.01752 were in group 1; patients with <0.01752 were included in group 2. Kruskal Wallis test was used to assess the normality of the distribution of the variables. Normally distributed numerical variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation., while those with non-normal distribution were expressed as the median (min-max). The categorical variables were expressed as numbers and percentages. The non-normally distributed variables were assessed with the Mann-Whitney U test, while normally distributed variables were assessed with an independent sample Student's t-test.

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The categorical variables were analysed with a chi-squared test. $P < 0.05$ was taken as statistical significance

RESULTS

A total of 209 patients (mean age: 66.74 ± 12.61 years) were included in this study. Patients were divided into two groups according to CAR levels. CAR cut-off value for predicting MACE was determined as 0.017 according to the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) analysis (Figure 1). During in-hospital and one-month follow-up, 35 patients developed MACE. In-hospital MACE was observed in 22 patients. In 1-month follow-up, additionally 13 patients developed MACE. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients are listed in [table 1](#). The patients with high CAR were older and there were more males when compared to patients low CAR group ($p=0.087$ and $p= 0.085$, respectively). The presence of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, congestive heart failure, peripheral vascular disease, and stroke/transient ischemic events were not statistically different between the two groups ($p > 0.05$ for all parameters). The laboratory tests and trans thoracic echocardiography results of the groups are listed in table 2. In the high CAR group, cholesterol parameters were significantly higher compared to low CAR group. There were no statistically significant differences in patients with high and low CAR in whole blood parameters, including white blood cell, haemoglobin, neutrophil, and platelet (P) count. Neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio(NLR) and serum immune inflammation(SII) index were found significantly higher and lymphocyte count was significantly lower in the high CAR group. CRP, albumin, and CRP/albumin level were significantly higher in high CAR patients compared to low CAR patients ($p<0.001$). There were no statistically significant differences in atrial fibrillation, paroxysmal atrial fibrillation, CHA2DS2- VASc score, and carotid artery lesion between patients with high and low CAR ($p > 0.05$ for all parameters). The left ventricle ejection fraction was similar in the two groups.

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Table 1. Demographic and clinical characteristics of the groups.

	Total (209)	High CAR (n=87)	Low CAR (n=122)	<i>p</i>
Male	117(56%)	54 (62.1%)	63 (51.6%)	0.087*
Age	66.74±12.61	64.48±11.36	67.92±13.86	0.085**
Smoking	38 (18.3%)	15 (17.4%)	23 (18.9%)	0.472*
History of CAD	30 (14.4%)	14 (16.3%)	16 (13.1%)	0.328*
HT	145 (69.7%)	61 (70.9%)	84 (68.9%)	0.435*
HL	19 (9.1%)	10 (11.6%)	9 (7.4%)	0.210*
DM	94 (45.2%)	36 (41.9%)	58 (47.5)	0.252*
CHF	18 (8.7%)	7 (8.1%)	11 (9)	0.516*
Prior CVE	40 (19.2%)	20 (23.3 %)	20 (16.4%)	0.145*
Carotid artery lesion	33 (15.9%)	15 (17.4%)	18 (14.9%)	0.378*
CHA2DS2- VASc	4.4±1.31	4.37±1.31	4.44 ± 1.31	0.706
Atrial fibrillation	46 (22.2%)	20 (23.3%)	26 (21.5%)	0.445*
Paroxysmal atrial fibrillation	35(16.9%)	14 (16.3%)	21 (17.4%)	0.497*
In-hospital mortality	21 (10.6%)	15 (17.4)	6 (4.9%)	0.003*
In-hospital MACE	22 (10.1%)	16 (18.6%)	6(4.9%)	<0.001
In-hospital mortality day	6.06 ± 1.8	4.33±0.51	6.48±0.79	0.260**
First-month mortality	9 (4.3%)	6 (7%)	3 (2.5%)	0.110
First-month mortality day	1.24±0.31	0.34±0.04	2.94±0.74	<0.001**
First-month MACE	13	10 (11.6%)	3 (2.5%)	0.008

CAD: Coronary artery disease; CHA₂DS₂-VASc score=congestive heart failure, hypertension, age, diabetes mellitus, prior stroke or TIA or thromboembolism, vascular disease, age, sex category; CHF: Chronic heart failure; CONUT: Controlling Nutritional Status; CRF: Chronic renal failure; CVE: Cerebrovascular events; DM: Diabetes mellitus; HL: Hyperlipidemia; HT: Hypertension; MACE: Major adverse cardiovascular event.

*: Fisher's Exact Test.
**: Independent sample T test

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Table 2. Laboratory tests and trans thoracic echocardiography results of the groups.

	High CAR (n=87)	Low CAR (n=122)	<i>p</i>
Glucose (mg/dL)	129.56 ± 50.52	140.76±68.83	0.209*
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	168 (160-221.75)	149 (143-204.5)	0.002**
LDL (mg/dL)	123 (89.75-149.6)	105 (75.3-138.0)	0.026**
Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	1.04 ±0.37	0.87±0.21	<0.001*
WBC (×10 ³ /μL)	9.54±2.99	8.77±2.58	0.055*
Neutrophil (×10 ³ /μL)	5.69 (4.66-7.28)	5.34(4.35-6.95)	0.183**
Lymphocyte (×10 ³ /μL)	1.97 (1.51-2.44)	2.15 (1.68-2.99)	0.009**
NLR	2.93 (2.23-3.87)	2.37 (1.74-3.43)	0.004**
SII	693.83 (518.02-1070.27)	561.90 (399.58-832.52)	0.003**
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	13.1 (11.65-14.6)	13.4(12.4-14.6)	0.209**
Platelets (×10 ³ /μL)	250.05±66.44	244.59±60.64	0.538*
CRP (mg/dL)	2.69±0.32	0.28±0.046	<0.001*
Albumin (g/L)	38.68±4.33	41.29±4.07	<0.001*
CRP/Albumin ratio	0.320 (0.235-0.554)	0.052 (0.037-0.055)	<0.001**
Ejection Fraction (%)	60 (60-60)	60 (57-60)	

CRP: C-reactive protein; dL: deciliter; g: Gram; HDL: High density lipoprotein; iqr: Interquartile range; L: Liter; LDL: Low density lipoprotein; mg: Miligram; uL: microliter; NLR: Neutrophils-to-Lymphocytes ratio; SII: Systemic immune-inflammation index, WBC: White blood cells.

*: Independent sample T-test

** : Mann Whitney U test

Figure. 1 Receiver operating characteristic curve to determine the optimal threshold for CRP-to-albumin ratio in patients with SVO in-hospital mortality (AUC: 0.702 *p*: 0.002 [CI:0.594-0.811]; 68.2% sensitivity, 65.6% specificity; CRP/Albumin = 0.017)

DISCUSSION

In this study, we investigated the prognostic role of CRP/albumin ratio (CAR) in AIS patients. Our study showed that high levels of CAR at admission were significantly associated with in-hospital and first-month MACE in patients with AIS. This study also showed that higher CRP and lower albumin levels were associated with high MACE rates in AIS patients.

We found few studies in the literature that determined the relationship between CAR and clinical outcomes in patients with acute stroke. In a study of 260 patients with acute ischemic stroke, high CAR levels were found to be an independent predictor of 90-day mortality [8]. In the study of Bai et al. in 236 patients with acute ischemic stroke, CAR was found to be an independent risk factor for 30-day mortality and demonstrated that it can be used in the evaluation of mortality in patients with acute ischemic stroke [11]. Elevated serum CAR levels were shown to predict symptomatic intracranial haemorrhage in AIS patients undergoing endovascular therapy [12]. To our knowledge, our study is the first to compare the relationship between in-patient and post-hospital 30-day mortality and CAR.

Studies have found that increased CRP or high-sensitive CRP levels are related with poor outcomes in AIS patients [13,14]. In the study conducted with Chinese patients, increased hs-CRP levels independently predicted the risk of all-cause death within 3 months [15]. Increased hs-CRP levels were also found to be associated with long-term mortality in AIS patients [16,17]. When only CRP levels were evaluated in our study, it was found to be a predictor for in-hospital mortality in proportion to CAR level.

Decreased albumin levels secondary to reduced malnutrition were found to be related with poor outcomes in AIS patients [18]. In the study conducted with 13 618 patients, low serum albumin levels predicted poor functional outcomes and mortality in patients with AIS or TIA [7]. In a study by Babu et al. in 560 ischemic stroke patients, they showed that relatively high albumin levels reduced adverse outcomes [19]. There was also found a correlation between low albumin levels and the development of atrial fibrillation which can cause cerebrovascular events [20]. In the presented study, a correlation was found between low albumin levels and increased mortality risk in AIS patients.

CAR, which is formed by dividing CRP into albumin, is thought to have higher prognostic accuracy than the use of these two parameters one by one. Elevated CAR levels were found to be associated with poor outcomes in other acute neurological pathologies and cardiovascular diseases besides acute ischemic stroke. CAR was found to be an independent risk factor for mortality in acute traumatic brain injury [21]. In a study of 379 patients with spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage, increased CAR was found to be associated with in-hospital mortality [22]. CAR was found to correlate with disease severity and poor outcome in aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage [23]. In a study conducted with 652 patients with the acute coronary syndrome, it was

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determined that increased CAR levels were associated with in-hospital and short-term major adverse cardiovascular events [24]. Plasma CAR levels have also been shown to predict clinical outcomes in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction [25].

Hematologic inflammatory parameters such as neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio, platelet-lymphocyte ratio, and serum inflammation index, which are other indicators of increased inflammation with CAR, were also found to be high in AIS patients with high mortality [26]. In a meta-analysis of 27124 acute stroke patients, an increased neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio was shown to be significantly associated with poor outcomes [27]. Like the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio, the platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio is was also found to be associated with poor outcomes after acute stroke [28,29]. Our study also found that high neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio, and serum inflammation index were associated with higher intra-hospital mortality, which is in line with other researches.

There are some limitations in this study. Our study was conducted in a single center and with a relatively small number of patients. It was made in a retrospective design. In our study, albumin and CRP levels were measured only at the beginning, but their levels may change over time, which may change their prognostic value.

CONCLUSION

CAR may be a risk score that can be used to predict in-hospital mortality in AIS patients based on both inflammation and nutrition. The CAR can provide important prognostic information in determining the mortality risk relative to CRP and albumin separately. Additional studies are needed to compare CAR levels with larger patient populations and long- and short-term mortality in AIS patients.

DECLARATIONS

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study was approved by Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University local ethics committee (09-22/05).

Availability of data and material

Not applicable.

Contributions

All authors contributed to: (1) substantial contributions to conception and design, or acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data, (2) drafting the article or revising it critically for important intellectual content, and, (3) final approval of the version to be published.

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